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A Traveller's Observations and Misinterpretations of Distant Land

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Francois Bernier, a French doctor visited India between 1658 and 1667. Besides providing information on India for Colbert, the finance minister of French monarch Louis XIV. Educated first in physiology and later in medicine at the University of Montpellier, Bernier (1620-1688) considered himself a modern man of science. In 1658 AD he sailed for Surat on the west coast of India and by March 1659 AD he joined the entourage of Dara Shikoh, as his personal physician. He wrote in detail about economic conditions and religious and social customs in northern India. His account of Indian travel is one of the pioneering works by which European intelligentsia came to know about oriental world.¹ He wanted to make use of his degree in India, thus unlike Roe² and Tavernier³, he had reason to be invested in the long-term health of the economy and nature of the government of his chosen country of medical practice.

Bernier reached India at the time of political turmoil at the highest level. War of succession was going on between the sons of Shahjahan, to whom Bernier refers as *Chah-jehan*. He had the opportunity to witness, understand and analyse the events, policies and personalities of the period of two great Mughal Emperors. Shahjahan died when Bernier was in Masulipattanam. Bernier's travelogue "*Travels in the Mughal Empire*" was published in 1670 AD. His writing is very vast and interesting. He not only describes the customs and work culture of Indians and Mughals, the source of education and knowledge and aims of their life but also tries to verify them with various facts and sources.

He describes the war of succession in detail in which all major *Umra* and *Mensabdars* of Mughal Empire took part. Events that took place after the war of succession and at the time of leaving India also caught his attention.

Bernier has portrayed the characters of eminent contemporaries in India. About Dara he writes "*Dara was not deficient in good qualities; he was courteous in conversation, quick at repartee, polite and extremely liberal but he entertained too exalted an opinion of him; believed he could accomplish everything by the powers of his*

mind...."⁴ He was expected to succeed the crown. Emperor also encouraged that expectation by placing an inferior throne and by authorising him to issue royal orders even to order a "*combat of elephants whenever he pleased; a distinction reserved only for the sovereign.*"⁵

But Bernier alleges the emperor of duplicity. He believes that Dara's father was never cordially attached to him. Because of growing influence of Dara the monarch was in constant fear of being poisoned. Before serving to the monarch Food was always checked and tasted by *Begum Saheb*, a close partisan of Dara. The emperor kept secret correspondence with Aurangzeb, of whose ability of government was always admired by him.⁶

About Sultan Shuja he says "He was sufficiently dextrous in management of an intrigue... knew how to win the friendship of great *Umra* ... he was too much a slave his pleasures."

Aurangzeb was devoid of the urbanity and courteous manners of Dara but had the great ability of taking judgement and was skilful in selecting for confidants such persons as were best qualified to serve him with ability and loyalty. Murad in Bernier's opinion was inferior to his three brothers in all respects.⁷

Begum Saheb, as he calls to Jahan Ara, was most beloved child of his father. Bernier also mentions that she exercised a powerful influence on the weightiest concerns. Bernier's one of the most important observation is about princesses not getting married in India.⁸ He reasons that after marriage that man may emerge as claimant to throne. Thus such situation was avoided.

The reason to it may be attributed to the seepage of *Rajput* ethos in to the Mughal family. He writes "*For, if marriage placed the two families on an unequal footing, clearly there could be no family superior to His Majesty's in his empire, where his daughter could marry*"⁹

While writing about Jahan Aara, Bernier could not resist himself of mentioning about bazaar gossips about princes.¹⁰ While describing the royal family, Bernier observes that in India names of the reigning family are similar.¹¹ He gives examples of Mumtaz

mahal , the crown of seraglio and Noor Jahan, the light of the world.

Being a Non Indian, Bernier analyses every Indian custom and rule in comparison to Europe. Let it be the naming pattern of ruling family or the law of escheat and end up with establishing the nobleness of European custom. That's why a prominent historian calls him 'shrewdest of all contemporary European witnesses'.¹² While summing up the war of succession, showing the decency of west, he mentions "In our quarter of the globe, the succession to the crown is settled in favour of the eldest by wise and fixed laws ; but in *Hindoustan* the right of governing is usually disputed by all the sons of the diseased monarch, each of whom is reduced to the cruel alternative of sacrificing his brothers, that he himself may reign..."¹³

Describing the events of civil war he mentions that Shahjahan was the partisan of Dara. Thus Bernier has rightly evaluated both- the event and the characters. But at some places he has misjudged. A place where Bernier's information is incorrect is that that Dara changed his elephant for a horse at the treacherous advice of Khalilullah Khan at a time when he had almost completely defeated Aurangzeb, and that this act on the part of Dara turned his assured victory into a rout.¹⁴ While the fact is that Dara dismounted from his elephant at a time of extreme danger, when he had lost all hope of victory. His elephant had become the easy target of the artillery accompanying Aurangzeb's division. There was no help for it. "*The wretched Prince hurriedly got down from his elephant and took horse, 'leaving his armour, weapons, and shoes behind' in the hawda.*"¹⁵ *The same has also been confirmed by the contemporary historians like Aquil Khan,¹⁶ Masum¹⁷, and Kambu.¹⁸*

Bernier has also highlighted the contemporary India's trade and commerce in a letter written to Colbert. He says that India imports various goods but there is no need to pay in gold and silver for this trade as foreign traders take local quality produces in return as they are more beneficial for them. Thus a considerable portion of world's gold and silver assimilate in India, as there are many ways of inflow seldom any to go.¹⁹

The basic reason for such barren practices, according to Bernier, was the absence of private property. Bernier argues "*The right of private property ... is the basis of all that is good and useful in the world ... and if we take a review of the different kingdoms in the world, we shall find that they prosper or decline according as this principle is acknowledged or contemned.*"²⁰

Bernier offers a very unkindly worded account of the Mughal Empire regarding its governance and economic stratagem. His intent is to dispel the western fallacy of as an exotic land of much reputed riches where all the residents are able to live a life of luxury. The doctor notes that "*on the contrary, the inhabitants have less the appearance of a moneyed people than those of many other parts of the globe.*"²¹ He emphasizes that there is a conspicuous disparity in the distribution of wealth between the haves and have-nots, the latter seemingly comprising virtually everyone whose veins do not course with royal blood.

The statement of Bernier is true that Mughal emperor is the master of *Umra*, *Manasabdars* and other offices and also that he is their paymaster. But his statement "the land throughout the empire is considered the property of sovereign"²² is highly misinterpreted. In India right to private property was available to everyone. Concept of private property was prevalent in India since ancient time. Bernier has misunderstood the law about the acquisition of unclaimed property by the monarch.²³

While writing on the life style of general public Bernier observes that though Mughal Empire has enormous inflow of Gold and silver. But there is lesser sign of prosperity among general public and he enumerates many reasons for that. Precious metals are melted again and again for making various articles; even larger quantity remains useless as that is transformed in ornaments. Thus in spite of the abundance of gold and Silver *Hindoustan* could not benefit.²⁴

Bernier has given important information about peasantry and land which gives a good account of the condition of agriculture of the period. Aghast by the apparently obdurate character of the Mughal ruler and the poor living conditions of the Indian peasants, Bernier felt obligated to write about the unjustness of the imperial rule. He declares that the tyrannical nature of rule has left a financial vacuum so great that it "*deprive[s] the peasant and artisan of the necessaries of life...*"²⁵ He further describes the abject poverty of the land, evident in the buildings and hovels of the towns that are constructed from "*earth, mud, and other retched materials*" presumably because the use of masonry is far beyond their financial means.

Bernier contends that all these problems have arisen from the absence of free enterprise in India, and subsequently the complete absence of a middle class. Furthermore, he argues there is a lack of personal incentive for Indian citizens to work hard because they are deprived reaping the economic

rewards of their labour and services, as practically all profits are collected in taxes by the emperor. Hence, he advocates the employment of free enterprise and recognition of private property in order to turn the plight of the ordinary citizen around.

He says that large portions of land were left untilled in absence of peasants and labourers because many of them could not survive the devilish demand and ill treatment of the local administration. Many of the peasants leave their places to avoid tyranny and oppression and find another mean of living in cantonments or mostly in cities.²⁶ These observations of Bernier are totally correct. The situation in that period was such that because of oppression land was left uncultivated and peasants use to take shelter with some *Zortalab Jamindars*.

Bernier has also produced analytical description about the composition and condition of the higher ruling class popular as *Omrah* or *Umra*. In this group many *Umra* were the adventurers arrived from many countries. In spite of getting the highest salaries of the age they always remain indebted. They ruin themselves financially by spending on their luxurious life style and lavishly organised parties.

Another cause disturbing their balance sheet was to make arrangements of very costly gifts to the emperor to be given at various occasions and festivals and to arrange for royal *harem*, which consists of wives, children, numerous servants, elephants and horsemen etc.²⁷ He describes in effect what he perceives to be an inherently flawed *mensabdar* system in which the local revenue collectors do not develop a sense of loyalty towards the subjects in their appropriated area due to the constant nature of their shuffling territories—a measure instated to reduce the probability of any one district staging a coup.

Bernier has made interesting observations about Hindus and specially of Brahmins. He says that Brahmins promote and propagate the superstition and myths as that helps them in maintaining their prosperity. He has mentioned about *Sati* and the custom of marrying young girls to the idol of *Jagannath*.

In a letter written to Monsieur Chapelain Bernier writes in detail about the indigenous majority to whom he calls *Gentiles*. He ridicules many Hindu customs and starts with eclipse of 1666 AD that he witnessed at Agra. He also reasons the cause of such eclipse festival through Hindu mythological story.²⁸

After commenting disapprovingly on ‘strange’ Hindu beliefs and rituals regarding eclipses, Bernier

remarks : ‘*The great Mogol, though a Mahometan, permit these ancient and superstitious practices; not wishing or not daring to disturb the Gentiles in the free exercise of their religion.*’ It was noted by Bernier, among others, that even in matters like *sati* the Mughals intervened only indirectly: ‘*They [the Muglahs] do not, indeed, forbid it (sati) by a positive law, because it is part of their policy to leave the idolatrous population, which is so much more numerous than their own.*’²⁹

He also draws his reader’s attention to the procession of *Jagannat* (*Jagannath*).³⁰ His observations are correct about the proceedings but here his ill understanding of local beliefs also gets uncovered. The carvings of *Yaksha*, *Naag*, and *Gandharva* etc. on the chariot are described by him as ‘*nearly resembling our monsters which we see depicted with two heads, being half man and half beast, gigantic and horrible heads, satyrs, apes, and devils.*’³¹

He is highly critical of Brahmins and, calls them knaves, is correct while alleging *Brahmens* of fuelling the gross errors and superstitions, like people throwing themselves in front of the chariot for sacrifice and girl getting married to the idol. But his description that how that girl is used by Brahmins and made to predict about the forthcoming year is surely a flight of imagination.³²

Sati, the forcible immolation of a new widow on her deceased husband’s funeral pyre, has been written upon by most of the travellers who travelled to India during medieval period. Bernier with his accurate observational ability is prominent among them. His account of *sati* rite gives a picturesque description. The practice had a few minor regional variations. In Gujarat and Awadh, *sati* was usually performed in a specially built wooden hut, while in Deccan, Rajasthan, Western India, the *sati* pyre was built in a deep pit.³³

Bernier’s letter to Monsieur Colbert may have also served in part to sublimate his guilt from being incapable of intervening eradicate the Hindu custom of *sati*.³⁴ Although he mentions the practice is not as prevalent as reported in earlier accounts of European travellers, Bernier is deeply disturbed when he bears witness firsthand to a widow barely twelve years of age being thrust into the fire against her will.³⁵ Perhaps he felt some amount of redemption in condemning the practices he perceived to be cruel in nature to his fellow countrymen, even if he was unable to voice his opinion to those whom it mattered.

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